

An Efficient Low-Cost Device for Sampling Exhaled Breath Condensate EBC

Mehran Khorshid,* Soroush Bakhshi Sichani, Dimna L. Barbosa Estrada, Werner Neefs, Alexander Clement, Gerhard Pohlmann, Ralph Epaud, Sophie Lanone, and Patrick Wagner

While exhaled breath condensate EBC is not yet used in routine clinical diagnostics and disease monitoring, recent publications indicate that exhaled air and EBC contain a wide range of molecular biomarkers that are characteristic of various medical conditions. This includes evidently lung disorders such as asthma, COPD, and cystic fibrosis, but also diabetes and several types of cancer go along with specific biomarkers exhaled from the airways. In addition, EBC samples can be collected in a non-invasive way and, due to their small volume, they can be easily stored frozen between collection and analysis. Several home-made EBC-collection systems for research purposes are documented in literature while there are also a few systems from commercial suppliers that are not yet certified as medical products. In this work, a novel collection device is presented in which the EBC is condensed and frozen inside stainless steel tubes, tightly surrounded by an aluminum cylinder that is precooled in a kitchen freezer. The device is low cost, easy to use by patients at home or in a clinic, and its collection efficiency of up to $500 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ of respiration is on the high side.

sampled using non-invasive methods suitable for individuals of all age groups, including even ventilated patients.^[1,6,7] Consequently, exhaled breath sampling has the potential to replace invasive and sometimes painful methodologies, such as nasal and bronchoalveolar lavage, as well as sputum induction.^[8,9] Specific diseases with a characteristic profile of molecular biomarkers are e.g. asthma,^[10] chronic obstructive pulmonary disease COPD,^[11] diabetes,^[3] and lung cancer.^[5] Moreover, drug abuse can also have its signature in exhaled breath.^[6] Exhaled breath analysis can be conducted directly in the gaseous state or in a liquid form known as exhaled breath condensate (EBC). While water vapor constitutes the primary component of EBC, it also contains aerosol particles with trace amounts of various biomarkers, including dissolved volatile organic compounds, non-volatile

metabolites, salts, lipids, proteins ($<1 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), as well as pathogens.^[4,5,9] These aerosol particles are generated when collapsed small airways reopen during inhalation.^[12] The main analytical technique for breath analysis is gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry.^[2] As EBC is collected from the respiratory fluid of the lungs,^[13] it is a sample type from which

1. Introduction

The analysis of exhaled breath is a promising methodology with the potential to detect a wide range of indicative biomarkers relevant to various metabolic conditions^[1-3] and respiratory diseases.^[4,5] Exhaled breath is easily available, and it can be

M. Khorshid, S. Bakhshi Sichani, D. L. Barbosa Estrada, W. Neefs, P. Wagner
 Department of Physics and Astronomy
 Laboratory for Soft Matter and Biophysics
 KU Leuven
 Celestijnenlaan 200 D, Leuven B-3001, Belgium
 E-mail: mehran.khorshid@kuleuven.be

A. Clement, G. Pohlmann
 Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine ITEM
 Nikolai-Fuchs-Str. 1, Hannover D-30625, Germany

R. Epaud
 Centre Hospitalier Intercommunal de Créteil
 Service de Pédiatrie Générale
 Centre de la mucoviscidose et Centre des Maladies Respiratoires Rare Respirare
 Université Paris Est Creteil
 INSERM
 IMRB
 Creteil F-94010, France
 S. Lanone
 Université Paris Est Creteil
 INSERM
 IMRB
 Creteil F-94010, France

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/adsr.202400020>

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DOI: [10.1002/adsr.202400020](https://doi.org/10.1002/adsr.202400020)

valuable information is expected in case of chronic respiratory diseases.^[14] Often, the exacerbation of symptoms is linked to well-known environmental factors of the *human exposome* concept, such as air pollution. These diseases are responsible for approximately 7 million deaths per year worldwide.^[15] Within the EU-funded REMEDIA project, we are developing a biosensor to monitor biomarkers related to COPD and cystic fibrosis (CF, also known as mucoviscidosis), two highly debilitating lung diseases.^[15] Examples of these molecular biomarkers include 3-nitrotyrosine (an indicator for oxidative stress) and the protein neutrophil elastase (an inflammation marker), showing higher concentrations in the EBC of COPD-, respectively CF patients as compared to healthy individuals.^[16,17] As a first step, we have designed an easy-to-use and cost-efficient device for collecting EBC samples.

The general idea of all EBC-sampling instruments is to bring the exhaled breath, being a water vapor at body temperature, into contact with a cold surface (the condenser). Upon cooling, the temperature of the vapor drops below its dew point and the vapor condenses at the surface, either as a liquid or frozen to ice. One can use condensers that have been precooled, e.g. in a freezer, condensers that are kept cold by contact with an ice bath, or active cooling with a Peltier element. Different embodiments of this principle are used in practice: The RTube device (Respiratory Research Inc., Austin TX, USA) is a commercially available EBC collection system and registered in the US as a Class 1 device *for research use only*, see ref. [18]. The EBC condenses at the inside of a polypropylene (PP) tube that is cooled from its outside by an aluminum sleeve; this sleeve is precooled in a freezer. After collection, the PP tube is sealed and shipped under cold conditions to an analytical lab, where the EBC is pooled with a plunger. The collection efficiency is mentioned as $200 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ for adults under tidal breathing, respectively 1.0 mL for a 7-min collection during which the tube is held upright. The RTube was e.g. used in a recent study to diagnose SARS-CoV-2 infections.^[19] Another commercial collector is the Turbo DECCS System 14 (Medivac Srl., Parma, Italy): The condenser is made of PP and its temperature can be regulated from 0°C down to -10°C using a Peltier cooler.^[20] According to the webpage of Medivac Srl., the device collects 1.5 to 3.0 mL of EBC during 10 to 15 min, corresponding to an efficiency of $150\text{--}200 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. A comparison between the RTube and the Turbo DECCS system can be found in ref. [21].

In recent work, Ilhamsya et al. developed an EBC-collection system in which the exhalate passes through a U-shaped channel that is mounted on a Peltier-cooled aluminum plate.^[22] The amount of collected EBC increased with decreasing temperature of the aluminum plate: At 8.5°C , the authors reported an EBC volume of $457 \mu\text{L}$ (standard deviation $92 \mu\text{L}$) for 10 exhalations in which the test person used the full vital volume. Sol and Quindry developed a home-made system, allowing the test persons to exhale through a Tygon tube, which was cooled in an ice bath at 0°C .^[23] For collection sessions of 10 min, they reported an EBC volume of $2.6 \pm 0.9 \text{ mL}$, corresponding to an efficiency of $260 \pm 90 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$. For detecting SARS-CoV-2 viral particles in EBC, Daniels and co-workers designed a face mask with an integrated cold trap that was covered with a hydrophobic Teflon layer.^[9,24] After precooling in a freezer, the face mask was worn for 5 min, and volumes of $400 \pm 150 \mu\text{L}$ EBC could be sampled by pipetting it out of the mask, followed by virus detection with aptamers

targeting the nucleoprotein and the spike protein of SARS-CoV-2. Literature mentions several other home-made and commercial systems, however the research systems stayed at the phase of demonstrator devices while not all commercial systems are on sale anymore. An overview of breath sampling in its gaseous form, without the condensation aspect, can be found in a review by Lawal and co-workers.^[25]

While EBC collection seems uncomplicated, there are variables that can affect the collected volume and presumably also the concentration of molecular biomarkers: Factors at the side of the patient include the duration of collection, the respiratory rate, and the breath volume per exhalation; even the posture can affect the so-called tidal breathing volume.^[26] A study by Czebe et al. compared different EBC collection systems with different materials of the condenser surface, being Teflon, PP, and glass^[27]: The total collected protein amount was highest for Teflon, less for PP, and lowest for glass (half the amount with Teflon). The material also affected mildly the pH of the EBC samples.^[27] For each material, the surface temperature had no influence on the amount of proteins, while the pH decreased slightly for lower condensation temperatures, likely due to entrapped CO_2 . One should keep in mind that the different materials refer to different devices. A direct comparison of different coatings with the same condensation device was performed by Rosias et al.^[28] For the protein marker 8-isoprostane, they found that silicone coatings collect a much higher amount than coatings made of aluminum, glass, polypropylene, and Teflon.^[28] Additional parameters that influence the quantity and composition of EBC are outlined in literature, see e.g.^[4,29–31] Interestingly, refs.^[29,31,32] provide a catalog of recommendations towards standardized or at least comparable EBC-sampling procedures. Furthermore, the references^[29,31] include detailed information on all molecular biomarkers known to be present in EBC.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Cooling Cylinders and Collection Tubes

The EBC is collected by freezing the EBC at the inner wall of two stainless steel tubes (alloy SAE 304) that are embedded in precooled aluminum cylinders, see **Figures 1** and **2**. The tubes had a total length of 26 cm, 20 cm length of the straight part, inner diameter of 5.0 mm, and an outer diameter of 6.0 mm. This type of tube serves normally as re-usable drinking straws since this alloy is corrosion resistant and suitable for applications in food context. Silicone mouth pieces are placed at the top end of the tubes. The tubes and mouth pieces of the brand Longzon *Eco-friendly straws* were purchased from Amazon. The water contact angle of the tubes' surface was $62.5^\circ \pm 1.8^\circ$ as measured with the sessile drop method using a DataPhysics OCA-25 contact-angle analyzer. A high contact angle facilitates the removal of fluid from the tubes.

The tubes are positioned next to each other (core-to-core distance 16.0 mm) in an aluminum-made cooling cylinder. The cylinders are made of pure aluminum (purchased from Dejong NV, Antwerp, Belgium) with 50 mm outer diameter, 220 mm length, and a mass of 1.180 kg per piece. Aluminum was chosen for its high heat capacity $c = 897 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ in combination with a high thermal conductivity $\kappa = 236 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$.^[33] To

Figure 1. Scheme of the collection device with all elements drawn to scale. The breath flows through the two mouthpieces downward and condenses and freezes at the inside of two stainless-steel tubes. The tubes are cooled via the aluminum-made cooling cylinder with an initial temperature of $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is possible to monitor the inner cylinder temperature with a thermocouple. Using two steel tubes in parallel reduces the required pressure for exhalation and increases the interface between the exhalate and the cold steel surface. The other elements serve for thermal insulation. The Petri dish holds back EBC that leaves the tubes unintentionally in liquid form. The device retrieves ca. 0.4 mL of EBC per minute, depending on the breathing mode. The condensed EBC is released into vials, see Figure 3.

Figure 2. From left to right: A test person inhales through the nose and exhales through the EBC collection device, the breath flows from the mouthpieces down two stainless steel tubes and leaves the device through the outlet openings at the bottom. Middle: After collection, the steel pipes are placed in the thawing station, and liquid (or frozen) EBC drops into vials, a close-up is shown in Figure 3. Right: One of the aluminum-made cooling cylinders used in this study. Disclaimer: The person in the photo did not collect EBC samples.

ensure an efficient removal of thermal energy from the exhaled air and promote freezing, the steel tubes fit, at room temperature, in sliding fit into the cooling cylinder. We mention that aluminum has a linear thermal expansion coefficient $\alpha = 23.6 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ that is higher than stainless steel with $17.3 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ K}^{-1}$ for SAE 304.^[33] Upon cooling from room- to freezer temperature ($-22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the diameter of the boreholes decreases stronger than the diameter of the tubes, which reduces a potential air gap between the tubes and the cylinder to a minimum. This stays valid under collection conditions, until the aluminum cylinder has warmed up again to ca. $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, allowing to remove the steel tubes.

To achieve the sliding fit, the boreholes were drilled in an automated CNC machine (Haas SuperMiniMill 1 with extended z-range), using extra-long jobber drills HSS N 6 \times 260 mm (manufacturer Garant) with 6.0 mm diameter. Drilling was performed in consecutive steps of 3.0 mm each with intermediate rinsing with coolant. Optical inspection did not exhibit any deviation from straightness along the boreholes. At the bottom end, the aluminum cylinders feature two press-fit bushings made of Poly-Flo (Imperial Eastman, 15 mm long, 3/8 inch outer- and 6.0 mm inner diameter) to prevent clogging of the steel tubes at the position where the exhaled breath has reached its lowest temperature. In order to monitor the temperature of the cooling cylinder in the freezer and during sampling, the cylinder had at the top end a blind borehole (depth 20 mm, diameter 1.0 mm) into which a type K thermocouple (0.5 mm diameter, TC Direct, Nederweert, The Netherlands) was fixed with heat-conducting silver paint.

2.2. Collection Holder and Thawing Station

For EBC collection as shown in Figure 2, the aluminum cylinder with the stainless-steel tubes is placed into a holder that brings the mouth pieces at a comfortable height while serving also as a thermal-insulation jacket around the cylinder. The bottom part is made of aluminum and hosts the following elements: two air outlets at the side, an open-hole Teflon disk (thickness 10 mm, outer diameter 80 mm, inner diameter 35 mm) on which the cylinder stands in upright position, and a disposable Petri dish to retain EBC in case that EBC drips out the steel tubes. The lateral side of the cylinder is embedded in a tube of thermally insulating polyethylene foam (Brico, Zaventem, Belgium) with 22 cm height, 50 mm inner-, and 80 mm outer diameter. The upper end of isolation foam is covered with a Teflon lid to prevent unintentional touching of the cylinder as long as it is at sub-zero temperatures during the collection.

After collection, the steel tubes are placed in a thawing holder, see Figure 2 and Figure 3. The holder consists of a stainless-steel disk with two pockets in which vials are placed. There are two vertical pillars holding a horizontal Teflon bar that can slide along the pillars. The stainless steel tubes are inserted into the Teflon bar through two tightly fitting bores. For thawing the EBC present in the steel tube, the Teflon bar is brought to its lowest position with the lower ends of the steel tube reaching into the vials. Humidity, condensing at the outer surface of the tubes, cannot reach the inside of the vials. The vials are sealable microcentrifuge tubes with 2.0 mL volume, purchased from VWR (Haasrode, Belgium). They consist of high quality polypropylene (PP) and are suitable for autoclavation up to $121\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ as well as

Figure 3. a) Zoomed-in photograph of the stainless-steel tubes that release EBC (liquid or still partly frozen) directly into the vials placed in the thawing station. Under normal conditions, there is no gap between the vials and the Teflon bar above it to avoid condensation of ambient humidity. b) Two vials with EBC were obtained after 5 min collection time, the total volume corresponds to ca. 2.0 mL, which was measured with the scale bars on the vials. For better visibility of the colorless EBC, 5 μL of turquoise ink was added to each vial using a calibrated pipet. The scale bar represents 20 mm, and the distance between the vials is equal in panels a) and b).

freezing down to $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Figure 3 depicts the thawing of frozen EBC directly into the vials and a typical EBC volume obtained after a 5-min collection session.

2.3. EBC Collection Protocol

The collection of EBC is performed in seven consecutive steps which a patient can principally perform at home. The recommendations given here are based on collection data that are discussed in detail in Section 3 of this article.

- The aluminum cylinder, with inserted stainless-steel tubes and mouth pieces, is placed in a freezer with a base temperature of -18 to $-22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The recommended cooling time is 4 to 5 h; longer cooling does not increase the volume of the EBC sample.
- Prior to EBC collection, we recommend a mouthwash and not using carbonated or alcoholic beverages for at least 1 hour before the collection.
- The cylinder is removed from the freezer using gloves and immediately placed in the holder. The donor, i.e. the test person in our study, can sit down or stand upright during collection, with the mouth pieces at a comfortable height. No differences in EBC volume were found between sitting and standing positions.
- For collection, the donor inhales through the nose and exhales through the mouth into the steel tubes at a rhythm of 10 respiratory cycles per minute. The 10 cycles min^{-1} was comfortable for the test person, higher frequencies are possible as well. The device samples ca. $400\text{ }\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$ and 5 min are sufficient to obtain 2.0 mL EBC. Collection sessions longer

than 6 min are not advisable to avoid thawing inside the steel tubes.

- Immediately after collection, the steel tubes are pulled out of the aluminum cylinder and transferred to the thawing station. Within 2 to 3 min, the EBC is released into the vials. Thawing can be speeded up by warming the outside of the steel tubes by hand, pressing gently on the mouth pieces removes the last EBC droplets from the steel tubes.
- The steel tubes and Teflon bar are removed from the thawing station and the EBC-filled vials are closed. They can be analyzed immediately or stored refrigerated at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ or lower until analysis.
- The aluminum cylinder, steel tubes, and mouth pieces are wiped at the outside and brushed at the inside with 70% EtOH to sterilize them. All parts are blown dry with humidity- and oil-free compressed air or nitrogen.

The different steps of this protocol have been visualized in a movie that can be obtained from the authors upon request. Regarding the sterilization step g), several methods are possible,^[34] but using 70% EtOH is the easiest to do by patients themselves. To keep the device simple and the comfort for the patient acceptable, collection was not done with nose clips, because this would require an additional air inlet and valves. Furthermore, a nose clip might form a barrier for patients with obstructed respiration such as in cases of asthma, COPD, and cystic fibrosis. During >50 tests of the device with the same donor, we did not observe that saliva entered the mouthpieces or tubes: Still, it is possible to add a saliva trap by using mouthpieces with an adapted shape that are available commercially and in custom 3D-printed designs.^[35]

2.4. Ethics Declaration

All samples were obtained intentionally from one healthy collaborator, who is a non-smoker and has a normal lung function, in order to keep the variability of the results low. He has given a written consent for the sampling of the EBC specimens. These samples were exclusively used to measure their volume and no other parameters were analyzed.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Cooling and Warming Kinetics

The aluminum cylinder with thermocouple and steel tubes was kept at room temperature $T_r = 22.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 90 min and then placed in a freezer (Samsung, RB31 FERNCSA) with a nominal base temperature $T_f = -22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The cooling down was followed with the thermocouple using a temperature measuring unit,^[36] and a thermocouple elongation fed through the rubber seal of the freezer. Figure 4 shows the cylinder temperature T as a function of time, $t = 0$ is the moment of insertion into the freezer. The fit curve is based on Newton's law of cooling in Equation 1a, and the corresponding law for heating in Equation 1b, see also refs. [36, 37]

$$T(t) = T_f + (T_r - T_f) \cdot \exp\{-k_c \cdot t\} \quad (1a)$$

$$T(t) = T_r - (T_r - T_f) \cdot \exp\{-k_w \cdot (t - t^*)\} \quad (1b)$$

Figure 4. Inner temperature T of an aluminum cooling cylinder as a function of time, the data represent one typical measurement. $T_r = 22\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is the room temperature and $T_f = -22\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is the freezer temperature. The cylinder is placed at $t_1 = 0\text{ h}$ inside the freezer and removed from the freezer at $t_2 = 6\text{ h}$ for EBC collection, which denotes the beginning of warming up to room temperature. The temperature rise of the cylinder during a 5-min EBC collection is shown in the insert. The solid lines for cooling and warming are exponential fits according to Newton's law given in Equations 1a and b, the values k_c and k_w are the time constants of this specific measurement.

The base temperature T_f is reached after $t = 3 - 4\text{ h}$, the fit has a goodness $R^2 = 0.988$, and the time constant has the value $k_c = (14.1 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3}\text{ min}^{-1}$ (average of three repetitions and standard deviation). Then, the cylinder was removed from the freezer and placed in the collection holder standing on the table. During 5 min of EBC collection, the cylinder temperature increased from -19.5 to $-7.0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, meaning that at the end of the collection the cylinder is still at sub-zero temperatures to guarantee that frozen EBC is not thawing instantly.

After collection, the cylinder was removed and placed upright on the table. The warming-up data can be fitted with the corresponding Newton's law of heating in Equation 1b: Here, t^* denotes the moment when removing the cylinder from the holder and $k_w = (19.7 \pm 1.9) \times 10^{-3}\text{ min}^{-1}$ is the time constant of warming. The goodness of the fit is $R^2 = 0.995$. The time constant for warming is higher than for cooling due to the fact that convective air flow is present under warming-up conditions, which is not the case for cooling. The temperature of the cylinder reaches $T = 15\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at 2 h after the collection and sterilization with EtOH can start. A fast warming up within 5 to 10 min is possible by rinsing with lukewarm water. In principle, the cylinder can also be cooled down faster than shown in Figure 4 by using a laboratory freezer at $-80\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, however this will result in clogging of the upper part of the tubes by frozen EBC.

3.2. Estimation of Airflow Parameters and Intraoral Exhaling Pressure

The test person exhaled through the device 10 times per minute and the volume per exhalation was $1.6 \pm 0.2\text{ L}$, meaning that

the breath probably included also portions from the deeper airways. The volume was determined by exhaling into sealed plastic bags through the two steel pipes with mouthpieces. Other exhalation modes, with smaller exhaled volumes, are described in Section 3.4. To calculate the volumetric flux, we use 1.6 L per exhalation. Dividing this over the two steel tubes, the flux Q per tube is $8.0\text{ L min}^{-1} = 1.3 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$. Taking the cross-section A of the tube into account, we get an average flow velocity $v = Q A^{-1} = 6.6\text{ m s}^{-1}$. To assess whether the breath flow is laminar or turbulent, we calculate the Reynolds number Re for the given situation:

$$Re = \frac{\rho v d}{\eta} \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of air (1.29 kg m^{-3}), the tube diameter d is 5.0 mm , and η is the viscosity of air ($2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$). This results in $Re = 2130 < 3000$, meaning that the airflow is still at the laminar side. Therefore, the law of Hagen-Poiseuille in Equation 3 can be used to link the flux Q through the tubes to the intraoral overpressure ΔP that generates this flux and to the flow resistance R_f of the tubes, see also Chapter 17 in ref. [38]

$$Q = \frac{\Delta P}{R_f} \quad \text{with} \quad R_f = \frac{8 \eta \ell}{\pi r^4} \quad (3)$$

Inserting the tube length $\ell = 0.26\text{ m}$ and its inner radius, we obtain $R_f = 3.4 \cdot 10^5\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s m}^{-3}$ for one tube. To this, we add the flow resistance of the mouth piece with a 14 mm long orifice and 2.0 mm inner radius. This results in an additional flow-resistance of $0.4 \cdot 10^5\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s m}^{-3}$, respectively $3.8 \cdot 10^5\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s m}^{-3}$ for the combination of tube and mouthpiece. During collection, two tubes are used in parallel, so that the total flow resistance is $R_f(\text{total}) \approx 1.9 \cdot 10^5\text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s m}^{-3}$. An R_f contribution by the bottom holder is negligibly small.

Using $Q(\text{total}) = 2.7 \cdot 10^{-4}\text{ m}^3\text{ s}^{-1}$, $R_f(\text{total})$ and Equation 3, we obtain an intraoral overpressure $\Delta P \approx 51\text{ Pa} \approx 0.5\text{ mbar}$. Since inhalation and exhalation are alternating, one may assume a maximum overpressure of 100 Pa (1 mbar) during the exhalation phases. This is in the lowest range of the pressure scale required for normal speech or playing a flute.[39] In conclusion, practically anybody, including patients with a lung disease, will be able to generate and maintain this pressure for at least a few min. Based on experience, an EBC donor may sometimes feel a slight increase of the resistance against exhaling when collecting EBC for $>4\text{ min}$: This is due to the growing layer of frozen EBC at the inside of the tubes, narrowing down their diameter. While this indicates that EBC is successfully collected, one can lower the volume per exhalation to keep the overpressure at a comfortable level. A complete clogging of one or both tubes by frozen EBC does not occur thanks to the Poly-Flo bushings shown in Figure 1.

3.3. Collection Efficiency Under Standard and Modified Conditions

3.3.1. Deep Exhalations with 10 Cycles Per Minute

The general idea is to keep the EBC collection time short and this starts with the optimal cooling time of the aluminum cylinders.

Table 1. Standard respiration conditions: EBC collection results for an exhalation rate of 10 times per minute. The aluminum cylinder was cooled for 3, 4, 5, and 6 h in a freezer at $-22\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The starting- and final temperatures are the cylinder temperatures when collection started, respectively finished. All data given in blue color refer to 5-min collections. The optimal cooling time is 4–5 h and for both durations, we performed also 4-min collections with the respective data given in red. All collections were performed between July and September 2023 with room temperatures between 22.0 and $29.7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and ambient relative humidities RH between 27.5% and 68.8% . All data are based on minimally three independent repetitions and the uncertainties are the standard deviations.

Cooling duration	3 h	4 h	5 h	6 h
Starting temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-18.8 ± 1.6	-20.0 ± 0.3 -19.5 ± 0.4	-20.0 ± 0.7 -19.2 ± 0.5	-19.7 ± 0.2
Final temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	-5.6 ± 0.9	-6.6 ± 0.5 -8.0 ± 0.5	-6.9 ± 0.9 -8.1 ± 0.8	-6.1 ± 1.0
EBC volume vials (mL)	1.68 ± 0.26	1.97 ± 0.16 1.75 ± 0.25	1.97 ± 0.16 1.66 ± 0.06	1.85 ± 0.26
EBC volume Petri dish ^{a)} (mL)	0.47 ± 0.35	0.25 ± 0.19 0.12 ± 0.16	0.02 ± 0.31 0.10 ± 0.10	0.35 ± 0.42
Total EBC volume (mL)	2.15 ± 0.12	2.21 ± 0.12 1.87 ± 0.23	1.99 ± 0.14 1.76 ± 0.05	2.20 ± 0.18
Collection efficiency ($\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$)	431 ± 23	442 ± 24 468 ± 58	400 ± 26 440 ± 13	440 ± 37

^{a)} Measurements without EBC in the Petri dish can cause averages higher than the standard deviation.

Figure 4 indicates that the cylinders reach their base temperature after 4 h in the freezer, meaning that a single cylinder can be used for several EBC collections per day. To study this in more detail, we performed collections with cylinders that were cooled for 3, 4, 5, and 6 h as shown in Table 1. The required EBC volume depends mainly on the intended downstream analysis of the sample (e.g. mass spectrometry) and a collection session should be kept short for the comfort of the test persons, and especially for patients' studies; in Table 1 we chose for 5, respectively 4 min. The exhalation-related water loss of an average adult is estimated at 350 mL during 24 h , corresponding to $240\text{ }\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$.^[38] For 5-min collections, we would expect a total volume of 1.2 mL . Under physical exercise, this water loss can increase up to $60\text{--}70\text{ mL h}^{-1}$.^[40]

While we obtained a total collected volume of ca. 2 mL for all cooling durations, three hours is deemed as too short since ca. 0.5 mL of EBC drops on average into the Petri dish. If necessary, also this portion can be retrieved with a pipette and used for downstream analysis. Four and five hours give equivalent results with the lowest "lost" fraction for 5 h of cooling. There is no further improvement of the data for 6 h of cooling, meaning that 4 to 5 h is the recommended cooling duration. In all cases, the cylinder had sub-zero temperatures at the end of the collection, which is e.g. not the case when using an RTube.^[41] The obtained volumes are larger than expected from the data in ref. [38], we attribute this to the slow but steady breathing rhythm with prolonged, deep exhalation phases. Generally, there is no loss of EBC into the Petri dish when the ambient temperature during collection does not exceed $21\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, meaning that the data in Table 1 were obtained under non-ideal temperature conditions. At low room temperatures, even 6-min collections are feasible with resulting volumes up to 2.5 mL in the vials. During all EBC collections, we recorded also the ambient relative humidity RH , but we did not observe a correlation between RH and the resulting volume of EBC.

Table 2. Modified respiration conditions: The table includes the data for tidal breathing and for an asthma-like respiration pattern. Tidal breathing was at a rate of $15\text{ cycles min}^{-1}$ with a flux $Q \approx 9\text{ L min}^{-1}$ through two steel tubes. In the simulated asthmatic state, the rate was $30\text{ cycles min}^{-1}$ with a flux $Q \approx 4.5\text{ L min}^{-1}$ that was exhaled through only one tube. The cylinder was cooled for 5 h and EBC collection was limited to 4 min. All collections were performed in triplicate in August 2023 with room temperatures between 22.2 and $27.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and RH between 44 and 76% . The uncertainties are standard deviations.

Cooling: 5 h Collections of 4 min	Tidal breathing 2 steel tubes	Simulated asthma 1 steel tube
EBC volume vials (mL)	1.45 ± 0.045	0.75 ± 0.05
EBC volume Petri dish (mL)	none	none
Total EBC volume (mL)	1.45 ± 0.045	0.75 ± 0.05
Collection efficiency ($\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$)	363 ± 11	188 ± 12

3.3.2. Tidal Breathing Condition and Simulated Asthma Attack

We considered also two different respiration modes, being tidal breathing of a healthy person and a simulated asthmatic condition. Both experiments were performed in three independent replicates with cooling the aluminum cylinders for 5 h and a 4-min collection time. For tidal breathing, the test person employed a rhythm of 15 respirations per minute with a volume of $0.6 \pm 0.1\text{ L}$ per exhalation as determined by exhaling through two steel tubes into sealed plastic bags. The obtained EBC volume was $1.45 \pm 0.045\text{ mL}$ ($363 \pm 11\text{ }\mu\text{L min}^{-1}$) and no EBC was found in the Petri dish, see Table 2. The rate of $15\text{ cycles min}^{-1}$ is the average between $14\text{ cycles min}^{-1}$ reported by Landers et al. for healthy adults in a sitting position and $16\text{ breaths min}^{-1}$ mentioned by Pleil and coworkers for adults at a normal activity level.^[26,42]

Regarding the simulated condition of an asthma attack, the test person exhaled through only one tube to mimic an obstructed exhalation, and respiration was kept shallow on purpose. The rate

was chosen as 30 cycles min^{-1} with an estimated volume of 0.15 ± 0.05 L per exhalation as checked with a sealed plastic bag. Here, we collected 0.75 ± 0.05 mL of EBC ($188 \pm 12 \mu\text{L min}^{-1}$), and again no EBC was seen in the Petri dish. In case of real asthma patients, it is evidently more comfortable to utilize the two tubes in parallel. In severe asthma attacks, the respiration rate can even exceed 30 cycles min^{-1} as reported by Papiris et al.^[43]

3.3.3. Test for Intrusion of Ambient Air Humidity

We also assessed whether ambient humidity condenses inside the steel tubes while operating the collection device. In theory, ambient humidity can enter the tubes through the mouth pieces (before and after the actual collection step) and through the air outlets of the bottom holder, see Figure 1. In practice, this is unlikely due to the quasi constant downstream of exhalate through the tubes. To test this, we simulated a 5-min collection without exhaling through the steel tubes while the mouth pieces were open. The aluminum cylinder had been cooled overnight and the test was performed on a humid day with 27.0 °C room temperature and RH 57.8%. It was impossible to extract any fluid from the steel tubes and visual inspection did not show humidity inside the tubes. In conclusion, the samples obtained in the tests of Tables 1 and 2 were pure EBC without dilution by ambient humidity. In addition, we monitored the temperature of the aluminum cylinder, which was -19.0 °C after removing it from the freezer and it increased only slightly to -16.6 °C after the simulated collection. This shows that the device has a good thermal insulation and that the temperature increase during real collections (see Table 1, top rows) is due to heat extracted from the exhaled breath itself.

4. Conclusion

Within this work, we have developed and tested a low-cost collection device for exhaled breath condensate, which is a prospective body fluid for the diagnosis and monitoring of lung disorders. For a collection time of only 4 min, the device samples ca. 1.5 mL of EBC (0.36 mL min^{-1}) in case of tidal breathing at an average rate. A slower rhythm characterized by long exhalation phases increases the volume to 1.9 mL and the efficiency to 0.48 mL min^{-1} . Hereby, the EBC contains likely also fractions from deeper regions of the lung. For a simulated asthmatic condition, the volume was reduced to 0.75 mL (0.19 mL min^{-1}). In this sense, EBC collection with the new device is fast and the sampled volumes are large. In both aspects, the device is at least on par or exceeds the specifications of other experimental or commercial instruments. In further research, we will assess whether stainless steel as condensing surface affects the concentration of relevant molecular biomarkers in the EBC samples. The chosen material is highly inert and molecules are trapped in a thin aqueous film that freezes rapidly at sub-zero temperatures. Therefore, one may expect that protein biomarkers will not denature during EBC collection.

Besides of the freezer for cooling the aluminum cylinders, the new instrument consumes no electricity and has no electrical parts. After collection, the EBC accumulates by gravity into small-volume vials so that the sample can be conveniently stored until

analysis with respect to molecular biomarkers. Furthermore, the time interval between starting a collection and the moment that the sample is ready for analysis (or freezing), is not >10 min during which the EBC is only in contact with inert stainless steel and medical-grade polypropylene. The consumables cost ca. 1 – 2 Euro per sample collection for the vials and the stainless-steel tubes, the latter can also be reused after sterilization. The instrument is compact and can be utilized for instance in a clinic, in a doctor's office, or by a patient at home since its handling requires only very little training. The intraoral overpressure for exhaling is especially low so that collecting will still be comfortable even in case that a saliva trap is added as an upgrade.

The collection device is not yet validated and certified as a medical instrument, meaning that it can currently be used only for research purposes. A first feasibility study on patients, is currently performed at the Fraunhofer Institute for Toxicology and Experimental Medicine ITEM in Hannover (Germany) for COPD patients and the Cystic Centre of Creteil (France) for patients suffering from cystic fibrosis or COPD. This way, results on EBC collection in a clinical setting and under medical supervision will become available shortly.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the European Union through the H2020 project REMEDIA (*Impact of Exosome on the Course of Lung Diseases*), grant no. 874753. The authors wish to thank Dries Dirx and Johan Morren, both in KU Leuven, cordially for the precision drilling of the cooling cylinders. Furthermore, we wish to thank Dr. Olaf Holz (Fraunhofer ITEM, Hannover, Germany) for his valuable contributions regarding breath-sampling technologies. Finally, the authors appreciate advice from Prof. Theodor Doll from Hannover Medical School regarding the intraoral overpressure for wind instruments.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

exhaled breath condensate EBC, heat and mass transfer, lung diseases, medical instrumentation, molecular biomarkers

Received: February 5, 2024
Published online:

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